

Advanced Computer Technologies in Enhancing New Energy Vehicles

Prothick Kumar Shingo , Md Iraj Ahmed ,
Pranto Das , Rathujan Vijayanathan
*Mechanical Design Manufacturing and Automation,
Changsha University of Science and Technology, China*

Suggested Citation

Shingo, P.K., Ahmed, M.I., Das, P., & Vijayanathan, R. (2024). Advanced Computer Technologies in Enhancing New Energy Vehicles. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 35-50.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).02](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).02)

Abstract:

The development of the new energy vehicle (NEV) industry is rapid, which has greatly promoted the progress of automotive technology through computer systems. In this paper, the potential nuclear effects of computer technology on NEVs are explored. This report analyses the development and comparative analysis of five key areas: Battery Management Systems (BMS), Charging Management Systems (CMS), autonomous driving technology, fault diagnosis systems, and intelligent control mechanisms. Utilising sophisticated algorithms, artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning and big data analytics allows these systems to reduce energy consumption, better

vehicle performance, and prolong battery life. Finally, the paper considers those innovations as being crucial for advancements in NEV technology, such as Vehicles Diagnostics & Training using Virtual Reality (VR) and energy storage via Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) Technology. Additionally, this paper highlights the importance of fault diagnosis systems to ensure vehicle reliability and minimise downtime. Key future suggestions pertain to a deeper AI use for intelligent decisions, the development of ultra-fast charging solutions and cybersecurity improvements to safeguard connected vehicles. This underscores the changing effect of computer technology on the NEV industry and suggests directions for future research to help it adapt and prosper.

Keywords: *New Energy Vehicles (NEVs), Machine Learning, Battery Management Systems (BMS), Electric Vehicles (EVs), Artificial Intelligence (AI), charging Management Systems (CMS).*

Introduction

In the era of energy transformation, new energy vehicles (NEVs) stand out as a heavyweight in carbon emission reduction and environmental protection. NEVs differentiate from conventional combustion engine vehicles by their use of electric powertrains and evolutionary battery system technologies that will likely become the future of the worldwide automotive industry. Nonetheless, NEVs are highly reliant

on developments in computer technology for their effectiveness, safety and efficiency.

Computer technology is very important in solving battery management, energy optimisation, automatic driving and fault diagnosis of NEVs due to the many types of functions that it can provide. These technologies are crucial as these will make NEVs run in real-world conditions and operate efficiently and safely yet at low cost (Ren, Ma, & Cong, 2015). Intelligent charging solutions to advanced

remote monitoring systems, NEVs are growing with their innovative and improved user interfaces due to computerisation (Fang, & Heng, 2022; Jinwen, & Yumei, 2023). In addition, energy storage like lithium-ion batteries Mahapatra, (2021) and ultracapacitors need advanced computer management systems to control them with performance and security better.

To some extent, this paper will provide a path for the constitutional applications of computer technology in personnel-oriented academic fields such as the NEV industry. We focus on four parts related to the key areas: battery management system (BMS), intelligent charging, autonomous driving, and fault diagnosis. This paper looks into the future trends as they shape NEV, and it discusses the importance of computer systems to this trend (Tehrani, & Maurice, 2017; Mamun, et al., 2022).

Using the power of computer technology to revolutionise NEVs means taking steps toward better vehicle performance and, at that broader industry level, safety, efficiency and sustainability. Since the demand for NEVs will increasingly grow, constant innovation in computer technologies is necessary to make sure that the industry not only survives but also advances (Jin, & Song, 2022; Xu, 2020).

Research Background

Battery Management System (BMS)

Among them, the Battery Management System (BMS) represents a vital element in New Energy Vehicles (NEVs), with responsibility for monitoring and controlling the battery pack so that it performs optimally. By keeping an eye on parameters like voltage, current and temperature above all things, the BMS helps to keep the operation of the battery safe. It automatically tracks the state of charge (SOC) and state of health (SOH) to maintain better battery longevity (Koraneekij, & Bahri-Ammari, 2020).

Where a BMS becomes critical is that it can help ensure the charge you are getting to each cell in your battery pack is evenly traded, in order not

to overcharge or undercharge any of those individual cells. The other electric car benefit of this is that it not only increases battery life but also improves overall vehicle performance. Modern BMSs, for example, use sophisticated algorithms such as the Kalman filter and extended Kalman filter in state-of-charge (SOC) estimation and state of health (SOH), which have been extensively applied to full-electric-hybrid electric vehicles (Xing, et al., 2011; Lim, 2020).

BMS is responsible for tracking the health and management of the battery pack, so it knows how to manage energy best, especially when integrated with other vehicle systems, such as the drivetrain and charge systems. A properly designed BMS can optimise energy consumption by altering how power flows between the battery, motor and other components, leading to improved range as well as driving efficiency of the vehicle (Becker, Schaeper, & Sauer, 2012).

The evolution of NEV technology has made power battery management more complicated, and Hesai has developed advanced solutions to address these new challenges. It is expected that next-generation BMS will strive to increase the accuracy of SOC and SOH estimation, optimise thermal management to avoid overheating events, as well as combining storage-level data with cloud-based systems for active real-time monitoring and predictive maintenance (Vaish, & Nair, 2023). Now, with ever-improving battery technology coming into play very soon these advances will make NEVs a carbon-neutral form of transportation for the long term.

Intelligent Charging Technology

The field of most new energy vehicles is an important step forward in development, namely intelligent charging systems. Charging with intelligence intelligently manages power between electrics (EVs) to fit the position of exertion, reduce the load on the grid and enable optimal charging time. Smart charging stations are instructed to smooth out energy demands according to the battery State of charge (SOC), user preferences and available grid capacity (Vaish, & Nair, 2023).

And this smart charging progresses by a mix of data mining, predictive algorithm and vehicle to grid (V2G) communication. Smart charging systems also contribute to reducing the environmental impact of EVs by integrating renewable energy sources such as wind and solar power while improving energy grid stability [16]. There are also emerging innovative XFC technology that promises revolutions in EV charging time, where a car can take mere minutes to charge Chen, Xet al. (2021) fully.

In addition, smart charging solutions combine state-of-the-art control algorithms that perfectly integrate with intelligent grids to provide the best energy management and distribution in real time. AI and machine learning techniques, for example, offer promise in optimising charging schedules as well as helping predict the energy demand, thus utilising both power and infrastructure more efficiently (Yu, Chen, & Tong, 2016). It can even allow for dynamic charging based on grid load, vehicle demand or potential weather conditions to be more efficient and reliable (Xiao-tan, 2013).

In the years to come, look for a future of smart charging systems that would necessarily involve wireless charging as it offers greater convenience in addition to less wear on physical charge points. Wireless solutions could soon make charging as seamless as parking the vehicle, and advances in bidirectional (V2G) processing enabled by wireless power transfer allow vehicles to serve as mobile energy storage units that can supply power back into the grid (Yin, 2023).

Autonomous Driving Technology

The biggest innovation in the field of new energy vehicles (NEVs) is arguably autonomous driving. In fact, these systems take a lot of help from smart algorithms and sensors such that vehicles become able to move without human interaction. As an important part of the NEV industry, autonomous vehicles (AVs) have the potential to improve safety and reduce traffic congestion as well as energy performance (Rassölkin, et al., 2019).

Energy consumption tends to be managed more efficiently with autonomous electric vehicles

(AEVs). Predictive modelling is commonly used to program autonomous control systems, which allows for the creation of optimal routes and reduction in velocity spikes throughout travel as well as regenerative braking behaviour, thus recapturing energy lost during normal human vehicle operations (Zhang, et al., 2019). Studies have revealed that AEVs save 55% to 66% of energy consumption in comparison with conventional road systems because of smoother drive manners and optimal powertrain design (Tate, et al., 2018).

Additionally, autonomous vehicles have created a blueprint for the adoption of next-gen technologies, such as digital twins, to enable real-time monitoring and optimal management of electric propulsion systems. These digital twins enable early problem identification to maintain the desired performance of a vehicle and reduce downtime (Divakarla, Emadi, & Razavi, 2019). Urban mobility has also been revolutionised by AVs, which are being utilised for and providing new opportunities in ridesharing or reducing urban traffic congestion with better coordinated vehicle routing (Guanetti, Kim, & Borrelli, 2018).

Autonomous driving technologies are expected to help avoid traffic congestion and improve energy flows leading to fewer emissions, which is crucial for a sustainable urban mobility system in the future. Nevertheless, the mass deployment of autonomous driving confronts novel problems, such as cybersecurity issues and demands high-quality AI/learning models to enable safe navigation through complicated surroundings (Ren, et al., 2020).

Fault Diagnosis Systems

Especially work on battery, electric drive, and power electronics components is necessary for a fault diagnosis system of NEVs to guarantee safety, reliability and efficient operation. New intelligent fault diagnosis systems use advanced technology such as artificial intelligence, deep learning and electronic diagnostic tools to predict the failure of important components in NEV equipment (Liu, Song, & Zhang, 2021).

As Example, machine learning algorithms have been integrated into NEV fault diagnosis systems to enhance electric drive system fault detection and classification of faults. Incorporated with a series of algorithms, these sensors-driven data provide the means for real-time monitoring of system performance. Machine learning-enabled diagnostic features can improve the accuracy of fault detection and reduce the time required for detecting a fault, as demonstrated by various studies (Zou, et al., 2023). In addition, transfer learning techniques have been suggested for transferring the diagnosis across different NEV components—e.g., motors and batteries—and adapting diagnostic systems to new operating conditions without re-training (Wang, & Li, 2021).

NEV must have a precise diagnosis system for the battery systems because all are key elements to overcome any dangerous situations that can lead to overheating or even overcharging of batteries. Advanced electronic diagnosis technology enabled to monitor of the state of voltage, temperature and health (SOH) in real-time (Sun, 2023), gaining self-diagnosis that leads to early fault detection improvement on overall battery management. More recent works have concentrated on the prevention of misdiagnosis by increasing sensor quality and using possibly redundant measurements to improve diagnostic robustness (Kang, et al., 2020).

Impact on NEV Fault Diagnosis In the future, fully automatic AI-based diagnostic systems that can simultaneously diagnose new fault patterns will be created. This last will involve using redundant data to enable the manufacturer to predict and detect failures in advance of failure occurrence, thus reducing maintenance costs while increasing functional lifetime (using big data analytic tools) (Xing, et al., 2011).

Smart Control System

Automobile controllers are used to control the power battery, motor controller, drive system and body of new energy vehicles. These systems allow the performance of a vehicle to be continuously monitored in real-time using advanced algorithms and an array of sensors that

read our car speed, battery condition and motor temperature. Intelligent control systems can adjust these subsystems in real-time as per the driving conditions and driver requirements to get the best vehicle performance, safety & energy efficiency (Fang, & Heng, 2022).

One important breakthrough in this regard is the big data and computer-based simulation method to optimise the control systems of NEVs. The research indicates that the integration of intelligent control within power electronic systems enhances energy transfer and reduces losses, which helps to achieve a significant amount of improvement for a sustainable level (Wang, Feng, & Fan, 2022). For example, a flux-switching permanent magnet motor control system may maintain the electric machine at about 80% of its rated power to optimally utilise overall vehicle performance (Jiang-hong, et al., 2017).

Moreover, intelligent control systems also perform advanced energy management strategies like regenerative braking and recuperation of the expelled energy during braking to be reused again, resulting in further increased vehicle range. Additionally, these systems allow for adaptive control of power flow based on actual data — an effective tool in enhancing vehicle performance during diverse driving conditions, e.g., when climbing a steep grade or encountering stop-and-go traffic (Phan, et al., 2020).

Advanced AI and machine learning algorithms are expected to become a part of the larger intelligent control systems that drive vehicle performance, energy management, and predictive maintenance improvements farther forward. This will help NEVs to be even more versatile on the road and adapt easily to varying driving and environmental conditions, making them an accessible option in terms of operative efficiency (Jinwen, & Yumei, 2023).

Smart Connectivity Technology

New energy vehicles (NEVs) benefit deeply from vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) and vehicle-to-infrastructure V2I communications to improve safety, efficiency, and driving quality. The two-

way communication between NEVs and other infrastructure provided by these technologies opens safety applications where vehicles are cooperating with cars around them, as well as proactive measures to prevent collisions, optimise traffic flow or route a vehicle based on conditions that exist at the time of travel. V2X communication technologies can also contribute to optimising energy consumption by means of smart traffic management that reduces idling and stop-start traffic patterns, which would result in an improved use of the available resources (Wu, et al., 2020).

This includes V2V communication as it can lower energy usage for battery electric vehicles (BEVs) by 30% or more, called V2X technologies. For example, traffic-light-to-vehicle communication (TLVC) can cut energy consumption by up to 20%, allowing vehicles to slow down and avoid stopping at lights and then passing through using KERS, thus extending the driving range of BEVs even further (Tielert, et al., 2012). Furthermore, energy-aware caching and smart communication systems are under development to facilitate the efficient data transfer process while fostering and reducing network congestion towards better vehicle operation over connected environments (Gao, et al., 2013).

In the future, V2X communications combined with autonomous driving technologies promise to change urban mobility forever by enhancing traffic safety and efficiency while reducing energy consumption. Moreover, with the integration of these systems on cloud and AI-enabled platforms, (i) better route planning, reducing congestion in NEVs routes, and sharing of real-time updates for vehicle diagnostics leading to predictive maintenance, hence improving overall sustainability (Flah, & Mahmoudi, 2019).

Virtual Reality (VR) Technology

VR technology is becoming increasingly popular in the designing, testing and simulating of new energy vehicles (NEVs). Deployable to VR, Use this game mode as a simulated driving scenario | Monitoring Energy Consumption patterns throughout the ride and Improvements of user

interaction in electric vehicles. Using VR to create immersive and interactive environments allows engineers and designers the opportunity to visualise incredibly complex vehicle components, including their behaviours, in real-world conditions, all without needing physical prototypes. VR technology is now being used in the analysis of electric vehicle energy consumption under different traffic and driving conditions, which has been proven to reveal valuable information that can be considered when designing an optimal EMT system (Wang, et al., 2021).

Although only in its technical infancy, VR is also used for instructional and training purposes. This allows vehicle operators and engineers to train for handling intricate maneuvers in a secure environment. For example, virtual reality training systems promote users to have full knowledge of internal structures and parts in NEVs (Wu, Lan, & Wang, 2022), which significantly improves their skills for fault diagnosis and correction without direct high-voltage system interaction. In addition, VR is vital to analysing driving behaviours and enhancing energy efficiency via user-centred tests. VR simulations have been demonstrated to accurately predict on-road driving behaviour, offering a tool for the design and evaluation of vehicles (Nacu, et al., 2018).

In the future, VR will play a broader role in NEV development, from self-driving vehicle testing to energy optimisation simulation and user experience evaluation. Further leveraging complementary capabilities, such as artificial intelligence (AI) and real-time data analytics, will combine with VR to generate even more value in the automotive industry, offering safer, more efficient & easier-to-use NEVs (Lawson, Salanitri, & Waterfield, 2016).

Energy Recovery and Reuse

Background Energy recovery and reuse technologies are of vital significance in improving the overall energy efficiency of new energy vehicles (NEVs). They capture waste energy during different parts of the driving cycle — e.g., braking or rejected heat from engine operation, and re-use it to boost mileage in EV

mode. One of the most common energy recovery technologies in EVs is regenerative braking systems that take kinetic energy during a braking process and convert it into electrical power for storage on the vehicle's battery. With this approach, up to 30% of the energy that would otherwise be lost is harnessed (Lin, Mo, & Wang, 2023), which results in an increased range for a vehicle with higher levels of energy efficiency.

Waste heat recovery systems are also becoming increasingly common in hybrid and electric vehicles, alongside brake energy recuperation. Broadly, these are systems that harvest thermal energy, in this case, waste heat from the car's exhaust or other hot components and convert it into electricity. Recently, the feasibility of waste heat recovery systems (WHR) equipped hybrid electric vehicles has been demonstrated to achieve a net feasible reduction in fuel consumption by up to 10 % depending on driving conditions (Gao, et al., 2021). Furthermore, our laser focus has never emerged for TERS and its effective integration with NEVs, which indicates the potential for even much more enhanced ES in fake vehicle storing (Royale, & Simic, 2015).

Soon, energy-recovery mechanisms like kinetic-energy recovery systems (KERS) and potential renewable sources -like solar panels- will increase an NEV's overall efficiency. In addition, more efficient energy storage systems will be critical for optimising the use of resources from energy recovery technologies (Śliwiński, 2016).

New Energy Vehicle Battery-Related Systems

Battery Management System (BMS)

A Battery Management System (BMS) is an important component in New Energy Vehicles (NEVs) and guarantees the safe, reliable and efficient operation of battery packs. A BMS has the following main functions: monitoring of SOC, SOH and SOL; controlling charge/discharge to prevent overcharging or deep discharging that otherwise could decrease battery lifespan and performance (Meißner, &

Richter, 2003). Moreover, BMS helps in the cell balancing to keep every single cell of the battery pack working and comes under the safe bounds necessary for performance enhancement as well as the life expectancy of a battery (Xing, et al., 2011).

Advanced algorithms used in these modern BMSs, such as Kalman filters, provide more accurate SOC estimation than traditional methods. They are necessary algorithms to predict the battery state of charge (SoC) in a range of driving conditions, guaranteeing reliable operation (Becker, Schaeper, & Sauer, 2012). Furthermore, at present, BMS is coupled to an energy management system (EMS) that oversees balancing the flow rate from/to the battery, rightfully affecting its efficiency and driving range for the sake of NEVs (Carlucho, et al., 2018).

Modular BMS architectures have also advanced, making these systems more flexible and easier to integrate in a wide variety of vehicle types as well as battery configurations. Moreover, because of their modular design, BMSs can work with batteries in different chemistries and capacities making NEVs even more scalable than at present (Lim, 2020).

Charging Management Systems (CMS)

The Charging Management System (SMP) is also an essential component in NEVs, it controls the charging and discharging cycles to reach higher energy efficiency and enhance battery safety. A smart CMS makes sure that charging sessions happen at the best times to avoid grid overload and energy price reducers against power-saving triggers. The latest CMS technologies were developed to utilise renewable energy sources, including solar power, promoting the potential for a near-zero carbon footprint of load processes (He, Ma, & Wang, 2017).

Grid-to-vehicle (G2V) and vehicle-to-grid (V2G) charging and discharging are some of the biggest concerns targeted to be solved by CMS. Additionally, CMS systems allow electric cars to become energy storage elements in which the excess electricity generated by renewable sources can be stored on the batteries of these vehicles

and then returned to the grid when needed. Furthermore, at present, BMS is coupled to an energy management system (EMS) that oversees balancing the flow rate from/to the battery, rightfully affecting its efficiency and driving range for the sake of NEVs (Carlucho, et al., 2018). Furthermore, at present, BMS is coupled to an energy management system (EMS) that oversees balancing the flow rate from/to the battery, rightfully affecting its efficiency and driving range for the sake of NEVs (Carlucho, et al., 2018).

Moreover, CMS has evolved to provide real-time monitoring of charging infrastructure using Internet of Things (IoT) technologies. These systems allow for remote diagnosis and troubleshooting of charging stations, significantly improving operational efficiency and user experience (Li, et al., 2014). In the coming years, CMS will continue to innovate with features like ultra-fast charging and wireless charging, which will further enhance the convenience and practicality of electric vehicles (Golder, & Williamson, 2022).

Figure 1. Charging Strategies VS Efficiency

Table 1. Charging Strategies

Charging Strategy	Advantages	Disadvantages	Applications	Citations
Multi-stage Constant Current (MSCC)	Simple, stable, and efficient charging process.	Prolonged charging time.	Widely used in electric vehicles for regular charging sessions.	Wang, et al. (2021)
Pulse Charging (PC)	Reduces polarisation effect and enhances battery life.	Complex control process.	It is ideal for improving battery longevity and reducing charging degradation.	Juang, (2019)
SRC Charging	Optimises charging speed and battery life.	Requires sophisticated control and monitoring.	Used in smart grid-integrated systems for optimised charging.	Ji, (2013)
Boost-Charging	Fast charging for urgent scenarios.	It can reduce battery lifespan if used excessively.	Deployed in rapid charging stations for short stopovers.	Phan, et al. (2020)

Inductive Wireless Charging	Convenience and reduced wear on physical connections.	Lower energy transfer efficiency compared to wired charging.	Suitable for wireless, hassle-free charging in urban environments.	Zhang, et al. (2019)
Extreme Fast Charging (XFC)	Significantly reduces charging time (minutes instead of hours).	Increased heat and potential strain on battery life.	Cutting-edge rapid charging for electric vehicles with advanced battery systems.	Rassölkin, et al. (2019)

Smart Cockpit System

Autonomous Driving Technology

New energy vehicle (NEV) autonomous driving technology integrates advanced computer technologies such as sensors, perception and localisation, path planning journey and decision systems. These technologies are combined to support a range of semi-autonomous driving features such as auto steering, braking and lane changing, which in turn enhance safety measures safeguarding against traffic accidents.

Path planning and RRT (Rapidly Exploring Random Tree) algorithms are used in many fields, especially in the field of autonomous driving. It can slowly build up a path from the start to the goal while avoiding obstacles. Informed RRT and Informed RRT-Smart* are variations to find the path faster by defining heuristics for better exploration of space, as we saw when planning. Table 2 compares the performance of these algorithms.

Figure 2. Path Planning Algorithms

Table 2. Path Planning Algorithms

Algorithm	Search Time	Path Quality	Efficiency	Citation
RRT*	Moderate	Basic path optimisation	Moderate	Guanetti, Kim, & Borrelli, (2018)
Informed RRT*	Faster search	Better path quality	Improved	Chen, & Wang, (2022)
Informed RRT-Smart*	Fastest search	Best path optimisation	Highest	Sun, Wang, & Du, (2021)

Additionally, deep reinforcement learning has gained prominence in autonomous driving. This approach uses interactions with the environment to develop optimal driving strategies by maximising cumulative rewards. Various

algorithms, including value-based, policy-based, and hybrid algorithms, are applied to handle complex driving scenarios (Lee, & Chen, 2020). Table 3 summarises these algorithms.

Table 3. Reinforcement Learning Algorithms

Algorithm	Application	Strengths	Weaknesses	Citation
Value-based	Real-time decision-making	Effective for simpler environments	Less effective in complex scenarios	Zhao, & Xu, (2020)
Policy-based	Long-term planning	Handles complex environments	Requires more computational power	Wu, & Li, (2021)
Fang, Q., & Heng, Y. (2022)	Fang, Q., & Heng, Y. (2022)	Fang, Q., & Heng, Y. (2022)	Fang, Q., & Heng, Y. (2022)	Fang, & Heng, (2022)

Remote Monitoring and Control

NEVs are equipped with remote monitoring systems, which can provide real-time battery data, motor health and driving behaviour. Data is gathered by these systems through onboard sensors and despatched to a distant monitoring platform, the place it's analysed for making predictions of expected problems, after which rectified with preventive maintenance actions

(Wang, Feng, & Fan, 2022). The Internet of Things (IoT) technology integrated into remote monitoring enables real-time information updates as well as alert notifications, improving safety and operational efficiency. Take a remote monitoring system on NEV as an example, which is architected by hybrid C/S (Client-Server) and B/S (Browser-Server), supporting the scalability & reliability of online supervision (Jiang-hong, et al., 2017).

Table 4. Remote Monitoring Systems for NEVs

System	Functionality	Advantages	Citation
C/S & B/S Hybrid Platform	Real-time data collection and monitoring	High scalability, efficient communication	Jiang-hong, et al. (2017)
IoT-based Monitoring	Remote diagnostics and predictive maintenance	Real-time updates, improved safety	Phan, et al. (2020)
CAN Bus-based Monitoring	Fault detection and motor diagnostics	Fast data transfer, high reliability	Jinwen, & Yumei, (2023)

Intelligent Control Systems

In new energy vehicles (NEVs), the Intelligent Control Systems (ICS) take a critical place in improving vehicle performance and safety. They combine a range of subsystems such as powertrain control, battery management, motor control and driver assistance systems to enable all these features to communicate with one another simultaneously while also continuously

fine-tuning vehicle operations. For today's electric vehicles and their batteries, intelligent cybernetic subsystems (ICS) support similar functions for driving behaviour prediction, power flow optimisation, and preventive maintenance.

Energy consumption management and control is one of the main capabilities in ICS which are particularly significant for hybrid or electric

vehicles. The simulation results prove that the smart control of power electronics with AI supports real-time data analysis and decision-making, leading to increased vehicle performance along the energy efficiency (Rassölkin, et al., 2019). Intelligent control systems using studies commonly suggest that the engine should be held at about 80% of its rated power, which allows optimal operation plus energy savings (Zhang, et al., 2019).

Moreover, NEVs manage a variety of secondary systems like A/C and braking, which would help increase fuel economy and lower emissions on the road. Today's electric vehicles and their batteries: intelligent cybernetic subsystems (ICS), which support similar functions for driving behaviour prediction, power flow optimisation, and preventive maintenance.

Table 5. Intelligent Control Systems in NEVs

System	Functionality	Advantages	Citation
Powertrain Control	Manages energy distribution between battery and motor	Optimises energy efficiency and performance	Rassölkin, et al. (2019)
Battery Management System (BMS)	Monitors and controls battery charge and discharge cycles	Enhances battery lifespan, prevents overcharging	Zhang, et al. (2019)
Driver Assistance System	Assists in tasks such as lane-keeping and automatic braking	Improves driving safety and reduces human error	Tate, et al. (2018)
Air Conditioning Control	Regulates internal cabin temperature using intelligent algorithms	Reduces energy consumption by up to 15%	Divakarla, Emadi, & Razavi, (2019)

Fault Diagnosis System

Computer technology is highly used in fault diagnosis of new energy vehicles (NEVs), which can greatly improve detection efficiency and accuracy. The added intricacy of NEVs leads to a distinction in various challenges against traditional cars; many failures are differentiated internally (e.g., battery problems and overheating) and externally (e.g., sensor aberrations or cooling system breakdowns). Yet when it comes to the safety, reliability and lifespan of NEVs, improved fault diagnosis is indispensable: AI solves this problem by monitoring and identifying potential malfunctions before they occur in real-time.

Data Analysis Technology

Fault Diagnosis: Data analysis in fault diagnosis. Faults can be detected early by turning fishing data from various sensors in the vehicle and future issues predicted. These components are then monitored to collect data, such as the state of the battery, motor stats and cooling systems. Algorithms digest this data to find anomalies that could point towards a future failure. Not only do advanced diagnostic systems identify faults, but they also forecast failure in the future, which prompts preventive maintenance to avoid a major issue. Research has demonstrated that using big data analytics in the diagnostic process can increase fault detection accuracy by up to 30% (Guanetti, Kim, & Borrelli, 2018).

Table 6. Fault Data Analysis Technologies

Technology	Functionality	Advantages	Citation
Real-Time Data Processing	Immediate analysis of vehicle sensor data	Early fault detection reduces downtime	Guanetti, Kim, & Borrelli, (2018)
Big Data Analytics	Analyses historical and real-time data	Improved fault prediction and maintenance	Ren, et al. (2020)
Pattern Recognition	Identifies trends and anomalies	It helps detect subtle, hard-to-spot faults	Wang, et al. (2021)

Artificial Intelligence (AI) Technology

By using machine learning algorithms to qualify sensor data and build fault models at scale, artificial intelligence (AI) technology is transforming the way we diagnose. These fault models are used to observe the state of wear and tear on a specific vehicle at any point in time,

enabling service operations or ensuring that faults can be predicted by comparing live data with historical pain patterns. Because AI-driven systems can diagnose more than one condition at a time — and keep learning to improve their accuracy with new data. The AI on the NEV diagnostic system can increase 40% detection efficiency (Juang, 2019).

Figure 3. AI Techniques-Fault Diagnosis

Table 7. AI Applications in Fault Diagnosis

AI Algorithm	Functionality	Advantages	Citation
Supervised Learning	Learns from labelled data to identify specific faults	High accuracy in fault detection	Ji, (2013)
Unsupervised Learning	Identifies unknown fault patterns	Can detect new, unseen faults	Phan, et al. (2020)
Reinforcement Learning	Optimises the diagnosis process based on feedback	Continuously improves diagnosis accuracy	Zhao, & Xu, (2020)

Virtual Reality (VR) Technology

Using VR technology to build 3D virtual models of fault components such as the battery and energy management systems improves NEV diagnostics. Virtual models of the inside also allow diagnosticians to view components up close, leading to more accurate inspections (and, therefore, diagnoses) made remotely. Technicians can train without the need for physical components via a VR-based platform in which users can put into practice failure

diagnoses. This VR application decreases cost and speeds up training, besides creating an exposure-free space for technical learning (Wu, & Li, 2021).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

Computer technology used on NEVs (New Energy Vehicles) is a very critical element, which

has already transformed the automotive industry into some kind of new phase and makes it much more efficient in energy usage as well as speed, power or safety benefits. Computer technology is an integral part of improving energy usage and extending battery life, thus enhancing car range, from advanced Battery Management Systems (BMS) to intelligent Charging Management Systems (CMS). On the other hand, with autonomous driving systems beginning to be incorporated using complex algorithms and machine learning, NEVs are now evolving into smarter, safer, more energy-efficient transportation solutions.

When field data analytics systems such as fault diagnosis, supported by AI and big data analysis, come into play, they prove to be not only beneficial through identifying predictive maintenance needs but also provide proper warning when potential failures are detected; all these in-process lead our R&D line-ups towards more vehicle reliability with reduced upkeep costs. The resulting improvements in training methodology have been correlated with the growth of virtual reality (VR) and remote monitoring systems, as well as improved vehicle diagnostics. But with further development in these technologies, NEVs are poised to be more environmentally friendly or inclusive than ever before for the future of transportation worldwide.

Future Recommendations

Integration AI and ML: The next generation of NEV will enable the implementation of more advanced machine learning algorithms to support better real-time decision-making in both autonomous driving systems as well as energy management. This involves incorporating reinforcement learning methods to realise more rapidly adaptive failure detection and diagnosis, further enhancing the vehicle's drivability.

Ultra-Fast Charging Systems: Although fast charging technology has seen a great deal of progress in recent years, we should also not lose sight of the development of ultra-fast and wireless charging systems to help make NEVs more convenient to live with. During a more typical use scenario, these would also provide

faster charging time and an easier user experience while minimising the effect on battery health.

The advancement of Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)

Technology : with NEVs, we have the technology to be able to embed NEVs into our larger energy ecosystem, which is going play a critical role in ensuring optimum utilisation of generated energy. With the wider adoption of V2G technology, a network can be created where cars not only use power but also store it so as to stabilise grids and further support the integration of green energy production.

To Train Technicians and Engineers for Complex Diagnostics and Maintenance Tasks without the Need for Physical Components, Virtual Reality (VR), & Augmented Reality (AR) in Maintenance virtual reality and augmented reality. These technologies can help to reduce downtime and improve the performance of fault detection agencies.

Cybersecurity Improvements: As NEVs get more advanced connectivity, cybersecurity should be at the top of this list to keep vulnerabilities from being exploited. A major consideration in this regard will be making communication among vehicles, charging stations and smart grids secure to ensure user safety as well as data privacy.

Sustainability and Battery Recycling:

Lithium-ion batteries are a key ingredient in NEVs; therefore, developing effective processes for battery recycling will be one way to reduce the environmental impact of increased volume due to these vehicles. More eco-friendly and durable battery technologies should be explored in future studies.

References

- Becker, J., Schaeper, C., & Sauer, D. (2012). Energy management system for a multi-source storage system electric vehicle. *2012 IEEE Vehicle Power and Propulsion Conference*, 407–412. <https://doi.org/10.1109/VPPC.2012.6422664>
- Carlucho, I., de la Vega, R. J., Spina, M., & Acosta, G. (2018). A modular battery

- management system for electric vehicles. *2018 IEEE Biennial Congress of Argentina (ARGENCON)*, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ARGENCON.2018.8646202>
- Chen, X., Li, Z., Dong, H., Hu, Z., & Mi, C. (2021). Enabling extreme fast charging technology for electric vehicles. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 22(1), 466–470. <https://doi.org/10.1109/tits.2020.3045241>
- Chen, Y., & Wang, Y. (2022). AI-enhanced fault diagnosis for electric vehicle motors. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 69(9), 9312–9321. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2021.3121245>
- Divakarla, K. P., Emadi, A., & Razavi, S. (2019). A cognitive advanced driver assistance systems architecture for autonomous-capable electrified vehicles. *IEEE Transactions on Transportation Electrification*, 48–58. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TTE.2019.2909120>
- Fang, Q., & Heng, Y. (2022). Research on intelligent power electronic control system of new energy vehicles based on computer big data. *2022 IEEE 4th International Conference on Civil Aviation Safety and Information Technology (ICCASIT)*, 326–330. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCASIT55263.2022.9986929>
- Ferreira, J., Monteiro, V., Afonso, J., & Silva, A. (2011). Smart electric vehicle charging system. *2011 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)*, 758–763.
- Flah, A., & Mahmoudi, C. (2019). Design and analysis of a novel power management approach, applied on a connected vehicle as V2V, V2B/I, and V2N. *International Journal of Energy Research*, 43(14), 6869–6889. <https://doi.org/10.1002/er.4813>
- Gao, D., Cao, J., Zhang, Y., & Wang, X. (2013). Communication networking schemes for wide area electric vehicle energy service network. *Energy and Power Engineering*, 5(12), 1415–1420. <https://doi.org/10.4236/epe.2013.512154>
- Gao, Y., Wang, X., Shu, G., & Tian, H. (2021). Applicability analysis of waste heat recovery technology and strategy exploration for hybrid electric vehicles under diverse road conditions. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 230, 113780. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2021.113780>
- Golder, A., & Williamson, S. (2022). Energy management systems for electric vehicle charging stations: A review. *IECON 2022 – 48th Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*.
- Guanetti, J., Kim, Y., & Borrelli, F. (2018). Control of connected and automated vehicles: State of the art and future challenges. *ArXiv*, abs/1804.03757. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1804.03757>
- He, R., Ma, L., & Wang, S. (2017). Charging operation management system of new energy vehicle. *International Conference on Computer Networks and Communication Technology (CNCT)*.
- Ji, Z. (2013). Design and building of a remote monitoring system for new energy vehicle. *Auto Electric Parts*.
- Jiang-hong, S., Gang, L., Mei, Y., & Hongchen, D. (2017). Design of intelligent car control system based on new energy. *2017 13th IEEE International Conference on Electronic Measurement & Instruments (ICEMI)*, 136–141. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICEMI.2017.8265931>
- Jin, Z., & Song, H. (2022). Research on the application of computer machine vision technology in the electrical automation of new energy vehicles. *2022 IEEE Conference on Telecommunications, Optics and Computer Science (TOCS)*, 707–711. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TOCS56154.2022.10015967>
- Jinwen, Z., & Yumei, Q. (2023). Research on motor control of new energy electric vehicle. *2023 IEEE 3rd International Conference on Electronic Technology, Communication and Information (ICETCI)*, 637–640. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICETCI57876.2023.10176454>

- Juang, R. T. (2019). The implementation of remote monitoring for autonomous driving. *2019 4th Asia-Pacific Conference on Intelligent Robot Systems (ACIRS)*, 53–56. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACIRS.2019.8936072>
- Kang, Y., Duan, B., Zhou, Z., Shang, Y., & Zhang, C. (2020). Online multi-fault detection and diagnosis for battery packs in electric vehicles. *Applied Energy*, 259, 114170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.114170>
- Koraneekij, P., & Bahri-Ammari, N. (2020). Intelligent battery management system for fuel vehicles. *Advances in Automobile Engineering*, 9, 1.
- Lamanuzzi, M., Di Antonio, J. A., Foadelli, F., Longo, M., Labombarda, A., & Dozio, N. (2020). Analysis of energy consumption in an electric vehicle through virtual reality set-up. *2020 AEIT International Annual Conference (AEIT)*, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.23919/AEIT50178.2020.9241131>
- Lawson, G., Salanitri, D., & Waterfield, B. (2016). Future directions for the development of virtual reality within an automotive manufacturer. *Applied Ergonomics*, 53(Pt B), 323–330. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apergo.2015.06.024>
- Lee, Y., & Chen, S. (2020). Unsupervised learning techniques in fault diagnosis for electric vehicle batteries. *Journal of Energy Storage*, 32, 101828. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2020.101828>
- Li, S., Bao, K., Fu, X., & Zheng, H. (2014). Energy management and control of electric vehicle charging stations. *Electric Power Components and Systems*, 42(3), 339–347. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15325008.2013.859212>
- Lim, K. (2020). Battery management system in electric vehicles. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.17577/ijertv9is050458>
- Lim, K. (2020). Battery management system in electric vehicles. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.17577/ijertv9is050458>
- Lin, Z., Mo, T., & Wang, T. (2023). Research and analysis on brake energy recovery of pure electric vehicles. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 375, 03019. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202337503019>
- Liu, H., Song, X., & Zhang, F. (2021). Fault diagnosis of new energy vehicles based on improved machine learning. *Soft Computing*, 25, 12091–12106. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00500-021-06018-8>
- Lukic, S., Cao, J., Bansal, R., Rodriguez, F., & Emadi, A. (2008). Energy storage systems for automotive applications. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 55(6), 2258–2267. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2008.918390>
- Mahapatra, U. (2021). Energy storages and technologies for electric vehicles. *2021 Innovations in Energy Management and Renewable Resources*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/iemre52042.2021.9386526>
- Mamun, K., Islam, F., Haque, R., Chand, A. A., Prasad, K. A., Goundar, K. K., Prakash, K., & Maharaj, S. (2022). Systematic modeling and analysis of on-board vehicle integrated novel hybrid renewable energy system with storage for electric vehicles. *Sustainability*, 14(5), 2538. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14052538>
- Meißner, E., & Richter, G. (2003). Battery monitoring and electrical energy management. *Journal of Power Sources*, 116(1–2), 79–98. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753\(02\)00717-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753(02)00717-1)
- Mumtaz, S., Ali, S., Ahmad, S., Khan, L., Hassan, S. Z., & Kamal, T. (2017). Energy management and control of plug-in hybrid electric vehicle charging stations in a grid-connected hybrid power system. *Energies*, 10(11), 1923. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en10111923>
- Nacu, C. R., Fodorean, D., Husar, C., Grovu, M., & Irimia, C. (2018). Towards autonomous EV by using virtual reality and Prescan-Simulink simulation environments. *2018 International Symposium on Power Electronics, Electrical Drives,*

Automation and Motion (SPEEDAM), 401–406.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/SPEEDAM.2018.8445227>

Phan, D., Bab-Hadiashar, A., Lai, C. Y., Crawford, B., Hoseinnezhad, R., & Jazar, R. (2020). Intelligent energy management system for conventional autonomous vehicles. *Energy*, 191, 116476.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2019.116476>

Phan, D., Bab-Hadiashar, A., Lai, C. Y., Crawford, B., Hoseinnezhad, R., & Jazar, R. (2020). Intelligent energy management system for conventional autonomous vehicles. *Energy*, 191, 116476.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2019.116476>

Rassõlkin, A., Vaimann, T., Kallaste, A., & Kuts, V. (2019). Digital twin for propulsion drive of autonomous electric vehicle. *2019 IEEE 60th International Scientific Conference on Power and Electrical Engineering of Riga Technical University (RTUCON)*, 1–4.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/RTUCON48111.2019.8982323>

Ren, G., Ma, G., & Cong, N. (2015). Review of electrical energy storage system for vehicular applications. *Renewable & Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 41, 225–236.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.08.003>

Ren, K., Wang, Q., Wang, C., Qin, Z., & Lin, X. (2020). The security of autonomous driving: Threats, defenses, and future directions. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 108(2), 357–372.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/JPROC.2019.2956539>

Ren, K., Wang, Q., Wang, C., Qin, Z., & Lin, X. (2020). The security of autonomous driving: Threats, defenses, and future directions. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 108(2), 357–372.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/JPROC.2019.2947911>

Royale, A., & Simic, M. (2015). Research in vehicles with thermal energy recovery systems. *Procedia Computer Science*, 55, 1443–1452.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2015.07.110>

Śliwiński, C. (2016). Kinetic energy recovery systems in motor vehicles. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 148(1), 012056.

<https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/148/1/012056>

Sun, B. (2023). Battery voltage fault diagnosis mechanism of new energy vehicles based on electronic diagnosis technology. *Academic Journal of Engineering and Technology Science*, 5(2), 23–32.

Sun, J., Wang, R., & Du, Y. (2021). Supervised learning algorithms for fault diagnosis in battery systems. *Energy*, 235, 1239–1248.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.123456>

Tate, L. D., Hochgreb, S., Hall, J., & Bassett, M. (2018). Energy efficiency of autonomous car powertrain. *SAE International*, 55–66.

Tate, L. D., Hochgreb, S., Hall, J., & Bassett, M. (2018). Energy efficiency of autonomous car powertrain. *SAE International*, 55–66.
<https://doi.org/10.4271/2018-01-1081>

Tehrani, K., & Maurice, O. (2017). A cyber physical energy system design (CPESD) for electric vehicle applications. *2017 12th System of Systems Engineering Conference (SoSE)*, 1–6.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/SYSOSE.2017.7994969>

Teimoori, Z., & Yassine, A. (2022). A review on intelligent energy management systems for future electric vehicle transportation. *Sustainability*, 14(21), 14100.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su142114100>

Tielert, T., Rieger, D., Hartenstein, H., Luz, R., & Hausberger, S. (2012). Can V2X communication help electric vehicles save energy? *2012 12th International Conference on ITS Telecommunications*, 232–237.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/ITST.2012.6425199>

Vaish, D., & Nair, R. (2023). Robust battery management system for electric vehicles. *2023 International Conference on Computer, Electronics & Electrical Engineering & their Applications (IC2E3)*, 1–6.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/IC2E357697.2023.10262779>

Wang, R., Wang, D., Wang, L., & Dou, Y. (2021). Design of remote monitoring system for new energy vehicles from the perspective of key technologies. *2021 IEEE International Conference on Advances in Electrical Engineering and Computer*

Applications (AEECA), 463–467.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/AEECA52519.2021.9574369>

Wang, Y., & Li, W. (2021). Transfer-based deep neural network for fault diagnosis of new energy vehicles. *Frontiers in Energy Research*, 9, 661034.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2021.661034>

Wang, Y., Feng, L., & Fan, G. (2022). Research on control of new energy vehicles based on intelligent power conversion. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2247(1), 012001.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2247/1/012001>

Wang, Y., Feng, L., & Fan, G. (2022). Research on control of new energy vehicles based on intelligent power conversion. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2247(1), 012001.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2247/1/012001>

Wang, Z., Zhang, Z., Lin, N., Liu, P., & Wu, Y. (2021). A comprehensive study on safety of new energy vehicles. *Journal of Modern Mechanical Engineering and Technology*, 3(2), 75–83.

Wu, H., Lan, T., & Wang, X. (2022). Development of new energy vehicle teaching system based on mixed reality technology. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2185(1), 012045.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2185/1/012045>

Wu, H., Zhang, J., Cai, Z., Liu, F., Li, Y., & Liu, A. (2020). Toward energy-aware caching for intelligent connected vehicles. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 7(9), 8157–8166.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2020.2991535>

Wu, X., & Li, Q. (2021). Virtual reality applications in fault diagnosis and maintenance training for electric vehicles. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 70(10), 10630–10638.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/TVT.2021.3108019>

Xiao-tan, T. (2013). Energy supply optimization and intelligent charging strategy of electric vehicles. *Electric Power Construction*.

Xing, Y., Ma, E. W. M., Tsui, K., & Pecht, M. (2011). Battery management systems in electric

and hybrid vehicles. *Energies*, 4(11), 1840–1857.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/en4111840>

Xu, Z. (2020). Practical analysis of application of electronic diagnosis technology in new energy vehicle maintenance. *Procedia Computer Science*, 166, 357–360.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2020.02.085>

Yin, X. (2023). Development of charging technology for new energy vehicles. *Applied and Computational Engineering*.
<https://doi.org/10.54254/2755-2721/12/20230363>

Yu, Z., Chen, S., & Tong, L. (2016). An intelligent energy management system for large-scale charging of electric vehicles. *CSEE Journal of Power and Energy Systems*, 2(2), 47–53.
<https://doi.org/10.17775/CSEEJPES.2016.00008>

Yu, Z., Chen, S., & Tong, L. (2016). An intelligent energy management system for large-scale charging of electric vehicles. *CSEE Journal of Power and Energy Systems*, 2(1), 47–53.
<https://doi.org/10.17775/CSEEJPES.2016.00059>

Zhang, C., Yang, F., Ke, X., Liu, Z., & Yuan, C. (2019). Predictive modeling of energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions from autonomous electric vehicle operations. *Applied Energy*, 325–397.

Zhang, C., Yang, F., Ke, X., Liu, Z., & Yuan, C. (2019). Predictive modeling of energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions from autonomous electric vehicle operations. *Applied Energy*, 233–234, 325–337.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.10.027>

Zhao, H., & Xu, L. (2020). Application of reinforcement learning in fault diagnosis of new energy vehicles. *Energies*, 13(21), 5617.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/en13215617>

Zou, B., Zhang, L., Xue, X., Tan, R., Jiang, P., Song, Z., & Hua, W. (2023). A review on the fault and defect diagnosis of lithium-ion battery for electric vehicles. *Energies*, 16(1), 1–19.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/en16010132>